

Larvicidal activity of zero valent iron nanoparticles against malarial and filarial vectors

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Abstract : Millions of deaths occur every year due to serious human diseases transmitted by mosquitoes. The usage of synthetic insecticides in controlling the vector mosquitoes, leads to adverse environmental effects and includes with high operational cost. The purpose of the current work was to investigate the larvicidal activity of synthesized zero valent iron nanoparticles (ZVI NPs) against *Culex quinquefasciatus* (*C. quinquefasciatus*) Say (Diptera : Culicidae) *Anopheles subpictus* (*A. subpictus*) Grassi. The TEM study revealed that the size of ZVI NPs was less than 100 nm with spherical morphology. Larvae were exposed to varying concentrations (50–250 mg/L) of synthesized ZVI NPs for 24 h. The synthesized ZVI NPs showed percent mortality of 41, 66, 76 and 100 against *C. quinquefasciatus* and 29, 44, 59, 83 and 100 against adults of *A. subpictus* at concentrations of 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/L, respectively. These results shows that synthesized ZVI NPs have the potential use for the control of *C. quinquefasciatus* and *A. subpictus*.

Keywords : Larvicidal activity, zero valent iron nanoparticles, mosquito larvae, malaria and filarial vectors.

Introduction

Considering vectors like filariasis, malaria, Japanese encephalitis, Dengue fever etc., which cause severe human diseases, WHO suggested to make sure a diminution in malaria at least 50% by 2010 and 75% by 2015¹. National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme in India is using dichlorodiphenyl-trichloroethane (DDT), organophosphates and pyrethroids, organophosphate temephos, methoprene as adulticides/larvicides for the last several decades in vector borne disease control programmes². Usual pesticides, like malathion, pyrethroides and DDT have several drawbacks in controlling vector borne diseases.

More than 30 crores people are challenged by malaria and among them about 10 lacs people die every year³. Recently, green nanochemistry approach is emerging as a tool to control vector parasites which are the chief vectors of alpha viruses causing Chikungunya and Dengue fever due to development of resistance to chemical insecticides.

In addition, highly ordered nanoparticles of different sizes and shapes have led to the development of new biocidal agents⁴. Bacterial proteins are used also as effective larvicides, but are technically and operationally intensive⁵.

Hence, environmentally safe, biodegradable and target specific vector controlling agents against parasites are the need of the hour to minimize the toxic and hazardous site effects of traditionally used insecticides. It is established that eradication of mosquitoes is possible if control in larvae stage is critically considered instead of adult stage control due to inability of movement of larvae from the habitats. Due to high efficacy and nontoxic effects on nontarget organisms, the microbial and botanical insecticides were being used for mosquito control now a days⁶.

Recently the efficacy studies of synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) have shown good larvicidal activity when tested against the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* (*C. quinquefasciatus*) and *A. subpictus*⁷.

The efficacy of synthesized Cu NPs was tested against the larvae of *Anopheles subpictus* (*A. subpictus*) and *C. quinquefasciatus*⁸. Larvicidal activity of double walled carbon nanotubes⁹ and Ni NPs¹⁰ are reported in the literature. This is the first report on the use of zero valent iron (ZVI) NPs as larvicidal agent against any vector.

ZVI NPs can reduce or degrade the contaminants very fast compared to the macroscale iron because of their larger surface area, higher reactivity and unique catalytic activity¹¹. They are redox active and produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) through Fenton chemistry¹². These properties of ZVI NPs could be effective in controlling of spread of malarial and filarial vectors as a potential larvicidal agent. The main objective of this study was to test out the application of ZVI NPs as a latent larvicidal agent towards filarial and malarial vectors.

Results and discussion

The powder XRD pattern (Fig. 1) of synthesized ZVI NPs shows a very intense peak at 44.71 and a less intense peak at 65.54 which could be assigned to (110) and (200) planes of cubic Fe respectively and matching with JCPDS No. 00-006-0696. The TEM images at different magnifications, SAED and EDX pattern are shown in Fig. 2. The TEM study reveals that the size of the ZVI NPs is less than 100 nm with spherical morphology (Fig. 2a). The formation of core-shell nanoparticles is very clear as shown in Fig. 2b. As per our previous study (Mandal *et al.* 2012a,b) the core was Fe⁰ and the shell was iron oxide (approx. 2–3 nm). The SAED pattern make known that the particles are amorphous in character and the pat-

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of zero valent iron nanoparticles.

Fig. 2. (a) TEM Image of nZVI at a bar scale of 100 nm, (b) TEM image of nZVI showing core-shell structure at a bar scale of 50 nm, (c) SAED pattern of nZVI and (d) EDX spectrum of nZVI.

terns are indexed as (110), (200) and (211) reflections (Fig. 2c). The EDX spectrum (Fig. 2d) shows the signals for oxygen and iron and no other contaminants are appeared which suggests that synthesized ZVI NPs are effectively free from impurities. The presence of unassigned carbon peak is come into view from adhesive carbon tape used in EDX studies.

In the present study, synthesized ZVI NPs shows percent mortality of 41, 66, 76, 100 and 100 against *C. quinquefasciatus* and 29, 44, 59, 83 and 100 against the adults of *A. subpictus* at 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/L concentrations, respectively. The LC₅₀ values of the synthesized ZVI NPs against the fourth instar larvae of *C. quinquefasciatus* are 64.17 mg/L, $r^2 = 0.933$ and $\chi^2 = 13.169$ and against *A. subpictus* are 108.87 mg/L, $r^2 = 0.992$ and $\chi^2 = 10.947$, respectively (Table 1). These results prove that the concentration of ZVI NPs played an important role in larvicidal activity. The control experiment without ZVI NPs solution shows zero mortality in the concurrent assay.

Numerous studies have revealed the antimicrobial activity of ZVI NPs^{13,14}. ZVI NPs have shown a bactericidal effect on *Escherichia coli*^{14,15}, and the same results were not observed with other iron NPs like micro-scale ZVI, maghemite NPs, and Fe³⁺ ions^{13,14}. ZVI NPs shows no effect on *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*) when compared with *E. coli* in bicarbonate-buffered (aerobic) medium¹⁶.

Table 1. Larvicidal activity of nano zerovalent iron towards *C. quinquefasciatus* and *A. subpictus*

Species	Concentrations (mg/L)	Percent mortality \pm SD	LC ₅₀ (mg/L) (LCL-UCL)	r^2	Slope	χ^2 (df = 4)
<i>C. quinquefasciatus</i>	50	41 \pm 0.14	64.17	0.933	76	13.169
	100	66 \pm 0.26	(52.62–78.26)			
	150	76 \pm 0.11				
	200	100 \pm 0.00				
	250	100 \pm 0.00				
<i>A. subpictus</i>	50	29 \pm 0.10	108.87	0.992	44	10.947
	100	44 \pm 0.11	(92.15–128.63)			
	150	59 \pm 0.10				
	200	83 \pm 0.13				
	250	100 \pm 0.00				

Footnotes : Control - Nil mortality. Significant at $p < 0.05$ level, LC₅₀ lethal concentration that kills 50% of the exposed larvae, UCL - upper confidence limit, LCL - lower confidence limit, χ^2 - chi-square, df - degree of freedom. Mean value of five replicates.

Chen *et al.* (2011) have reported that the surrounded floccus on the *E. coli* and ZVI NPs surface decreases the zeta potential of NPs from 30 to -45 mV which results in minimization of direct contact of NPs with bacteria due to electrostatic hinderance, which lessen its toxicity. Recently Mahdy *et al.* (2012) have also reported toxicity of ZVI NPs on *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) with a minimal inhibitory concentration of 30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, whereas growth was completely inhibited at concentrations of 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ¹⁷. No report is available on the larvicidal activity of ZVI NPs against any parasitic vectors. This is the first report on larvicidal activity of ZVI NPs against malarial and filarial vectors. In this study the maximum efficacy of ZVI NPs against the larvae of *C. quinquefasciatus* (LC₅₀ = 64.17 mg/L; r^2 = 0.933) and *A. subpictus* (LC₅₀ = 108.87 mg/L; r^2 = 0.992) respectively suggested that its larvicidal doses were slightly higher than other metal nanoparticles^{7,8,17,18}.

Many toxicity mechanisms have been proposed¹⁹, including cell membrane integrity disruption²⁰, respiration interference²¹ and damage of enzymatic proteins or DNA caused by metal ions release from NPs²². The bactericidal effect is unique property of ZVI NPs, and was not seen in other variants of iron-based materials. Aerial oxidation of ZVI NPs forms iron oxide layer on surface of the ZVI NPs surface²³. The direct electron transfer from iron may perturb the enzymatic function of *E. coli*'s external membrane protein. Since it produces reactive oxygen species (ROS) though Fenton chemistry¹², these

highly reactive species cause its larvicidal activity towards the larvae of *C. quinquefasciatus* and *A. subpictus*. In addition, oxygen-induced corrosion leads to formation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ in bulk phase under air-saturated conditions which does not significantly contribute to *E. coli* inactivation which merits the use of ZVI NPs as potential larvicidal agent in the coming days.

Experimental

Synthesis of ZVI NPs : The method followed for synthesizing ZVI NPs was previously reported elsewhere²⁴.

Characterization of ZVI NP : Purified ZVI NPs were analyzed using X-ray diffraction (Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer at Cu K α radiation, λ = 1.54 Å). TEM studies of ZVI NPs were done using JEOL JEM 2100 High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope operated at an accelerated voltage of 200 KV. The SAED pattern confirmed the Bragg's angles similar to particles in the range of nano size. The energy dispersive electron X-ray analysis (EDX) pattern was recorded to check elemental composition.

Larvicidal bioassay : Toxicity test of the synthesized ZVI NPs was carried out by introducing 20 mosquito larvae in 200 mL of double distilled water (sterilized) with ZVI NPs in a 250 mL beaker. The NPs solutions were then diluted to the desired concentrations ranging from 50–250 mg/L. Each test included a set of control groups in distilled water with three replicates for each concentration. After 24 h mortality was assessed to check

the acute toxicities on fourth instar larvae of *C. quinquefasciatus* and adult *A. subpictus*.

Dose-response bioassay : To check the larvicidal activity of ZVI NPs towards fourth instar larvae of *C. quinquefasciatus* and adult *A. subpictus*, the ZVI NPs were subjected to dose-response bioassay. Different concentrations from 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/L (Synthesized ZVI NPs) were prepared for larvicidal activity on parasites. After 24 h of exposure, the number of dead larvae was counted and the percentage of mortality was taken as average of three replicates. However, at the end of 24 h, the selected test samples turned out to be equal in their toxic potential among themselves.

Data analysis : To calculate LC₅₀, the average larval mortality data was subjected to probit analysis and the software developed by Reddy *et al.* (1992) was used to calculate other statistics at 95% fiducial limits of upper confidence limit and lower confidence limit, and chi-square values.

Conclusion

In the present investigation, chemically synthesized ZVI NPs exhibited a high larvicidal activity and to the best of our knowledge, this is the only report on the larvicidal activity of ZVI NPs against *C. quinquefasciatus* and *A. subpictus* under ambient conditions indicates that ZVI NPs have good application for use as an alternate mosquito larvicide. More research is urgently needed to evaluate its potentiality as an alternate mosquito larvicide due to its low cost, easy availability of sources and non-toxic nature.

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